

**THE WORLD OF THE LANGUAGE OF LIFE: EARLY PROFILING AS A PRACTICE OF
PREPARATION FOR STUDY, LIFE AND WORK**

Kulsharipova Z.,

*Research Supervisor: Ph. D.,
Associate Professor of Margulan University
Pavlodar, Kazakhstan*

Baklanova K.,

*Master's degree in Pedagogical sciences
EFL teacher of Ainakol Secondary school,
Pavlodar, Kazakhstan*

Mekezhanova D.,

*Master's degree student of "Pedagogy and psychology",
Higher School of Pedagogy
Pavlodar Pedagogical University
Pavlodar, Kazakhstan*

Skakova A.,

*Master's degree student of "Pedagogy and psychology",
Higher School of Pedagogy
Pavlodar Pedagogical University
Pavlodar, Kazakhstan*

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Abstract

The problem of early profiling of primary school children age is one of the first places among other social and psychological problems. The modern schoolboy lives in a world that is complex in its content and ability to socialize. Even considering that it is currently very difficult to assess the problems of early profiling of students, we can say that the scale of this phenomenon is growing by many criteria.

Primary school teachers and school psychologists note that children of primary school age are most sensitive to social and psychological stress. It is at this age that there is a sharp increase in conflict, undisciplined, self-control students. This is due to many reasons. Let's look at them in our article, IPT (individual profile trajectory of learning).

Keywords: early profiling, preparation for study, life, and work, technologies of early profiling, and UNDER (individual profile training trajectory).

The problem of early prevention of primary school children occupies one of the first places among other socio-psychological problems. A modern pupil lives in a complex world in terms of content and socialization. Given that it is currently very difficult to assess the problems of early profiling of students, we can say that the scale of this phenomenon is growing by many criteria.

Primary school teachers and school psychologists note that children of primary school age are most sensitive to social and psychological stress. It was at this age that the number of quarrelsome, disordered, disobedient schoolchildren sharply increased. This is due to many reasons. Let us look at them in our article.

The problem of early profiling of primary school children occupies one of the first places among other social and psychological problems. A modern pupil lives in a world that is complex in its content and ability to socialize. Even considering that it is currently very difficult to assess the problems of early profiling of students, we can say that the scale of this phenomenon is growing by many criteria.

Primary school teachers and school psychologists note that children of primary school age are most sensitive to social and psychological stresses. It is at this

age that there is a sharp increase in conflict, undisciplined, and unable to control themselves. This is due to many reasons.

Let us look at them in our article.

At present, scientific and technical transformations are taking place at a rapid pace, which imposes new requirements on modern schoolchildren. The task of teachers during the application of the updated program is to instill in students the main profile areas, which will help to form a deeper respect for work, to be more tolerant in terms of interaction, to take responsibility for others, to be a healthy and disciplined person as a future competitive professional.

In our opinion, school education imposes excessive demands on students in the updated programs, not only in high school but also in primary classes, which leads to the appearance of mental overload, not accepting the results of educational activities, and conscious or unconscious dissatisfaction with the characteristics of characteristic actions.

And here these painful experiences occur in combination with negative emotions, which form an inferiority complex and, as a result, unstable behavior occurs. It is thought that a favorable emotional climate in the school team may be one of the reasons for the increase in unstable behavior of children at the initial

stage of training, where the teacher is removed from performing his duties to unite the team. Without proper pedagogical guidance, the laws of collective life in the classroom can be replaced by strict laws of the group and be aimed at suppressing individual students, which in turn is another reason for destabilizing relationships.

The defining factor in the information school community is the formation and development of an early professional culture of the individual. To form an early profile culture of the individual, it is necessary to understand what are the foundations of early profiling as a rule and law of continuity of the development of a value worldview for the future profession [1, 2].

Early profiling is also a process of becoming a person. The formation of a personality depends significantly on the totality of conditions characteristic of a particular socio-economic situation, and therefore the learning process provides for it as a component of the socialization of the student's personality.

The essence of early profiling as a component of socialization is that in the process its students were formed as members of the society to which they will be implemented as future pros. The school is a place of early profiling and should be implemented through the

technology of modeling the IPT (individual profile trajectory of learning) of each member of the school community individually to develop the basic social values, norms, and patterns of behavior in the group.

At the same time, at a certain stage of training, it is the socialization factor that begins to have a significant impact on the success of training in the system of early profiling of the child. To study the features of the quality of early education profiling in network profile training, it is necessary to determine such characteristics of network projects of the profile direction of primary education, which mainly determines its change. First of all, these characteristics include the conditions for the teacher to design an individual profile learning trajectory.

Activation of early profiling as specialized creative abilities directs the General activity of students to increase the level of specialized cognitive and creative activity. Quality of education in online profile classes [3].

Analyzing various options for completing specialized classes for younger students, we have developed the following principles and settings for early profiling (Table 1).

Table 1

Principles and settings for early profiling younger students in specialized classes.

I principle	II principle	III principle
analysis of the most effective and optimally satisfying the interests and needs of students and designing IPT as options for recruiting a contingent of student profile classes;	Selection of technology for modeling conditions of high reliability and efficiency of control and diagnostic methods of enrollment in specialized classes by students who demonstrate high motivation to the concept of " quality of knowledge»;	The organizational and pedagogical approach recommends not using of competitive selection because the grades do not always correspond to the actual knowledge of students.

The advantage of these options for setting primary school teachers is cost-effectiveness and morality.

First of all, at the stages of early profiling, teachers are recommended to have the skills to develop not only educational and cognitive activities, and this is the main factor for early profiling. Primary school students learn phonetics and increase their vocabulary, which allows them to master complex forms of speech activity. Visual-imaginative thinking dominates, and there is a gradual transition to the abstract-logical level of mental activity. It is important to be able to manage the processes of perception, which in the beginning is characterized by the formation of perceptual and intellectual actions as a system of thinking that forms bright positive emotions in children in the process of their creative interaction and communication.

Technology early specialization as mentioned above requires primary school teachers' careful design of actions. The logic of knowledge as the product of the results of knowledge and successful completion of an individual profile learning path for each student taking into account personal motivation, future self-determination, and value-semantic choice, providing the unity of the design stages of goal-promoting value-target each student awareness and acceptance of a personally significant goals of special education [4].

The system of indicators and criteria for scientific research of profile development at the initial stage of primary school education is one of the main issues of our research

We should not forget the fact that there is no specific system for identifying indicators, criteria, and levels of the early profiling process.

Using the "Profile-educational tracks" at the stages of early profiling, we defined a system of indicators and criteria for scientific research.

IPT design technology for early profiling is the basis for selecting criteria and levels of the process of cognitive development and as a level of preservation of psychological and mental health.

The planned results of training in IPT are a system of direct vision of the results by the student and the teacher, which give an idea of the status actions of the student and the teacher: personal, regulatory, communicative, cognitive, refracted through the specifics of technological actions of a particular subject. The teacher is the arbiter of regulating relationships.

The teacher, tracking the results of monitoring the development of specialized abilities at the stages of profiling, makes it possible to conclude how and in what direction it is necessary to build the stages of early

profiling as a process where the level of achievement increases for each student.

The development and implementation of quality methods and technologies of preventive impact/interaction as a powerful resource that ensures the success of the process of formation and growth of the individual is essential in the prevention of juvenile delinquency. To form an early profile culture of the individual, it is necessary to understand what are the foundations of early profiling as a rule and law of continuity of the development of a value worldview for the future profession [3,4].

Early profiling is also a process of personal development. The formation of a personality depends significantly on the totality of conditions characteristic of a particular socio-economic situation, and therefore the learning process provides for it as a component of the socialization of the student's personality [5].

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